

EVALUATIVE OBSERVATION ON D.H. LAWRENCE'S EPISTOLARY ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this study have seen the development of the understanding of the significance of Lawrence's correspondence, and of publishing all that is available, both letters from him and to him. His letters have been analysed in general terms to show the wide variety of voices Lawrence used, and the high quality of his letters.

D.H. Lawrence's renowned creativity is conspicuous in his letters. He wrote to aristocrats, fellow authors, painters, publishers, and others from the intelligentsia--but with equal concern to his sisters, a childhood friend suffering from tuberculosis, a post office clerk or an Italian servant-girl. Lawrence reveled in the act of communication, using a direct, unvarnished but invariably vivid style appropriate to each correspondent. In the book, over 330 of Lawrence's letters, carefully chosen from the authoritative seven-volume Cambridge Edition exemplify Lawrence's artistry and humanness. In his introductory essay James T. Boulton provides a rare critical assessment of Lawrence's epistolary achievement.

First of all, I am going to put the issues raised here into context and explore why they are important, dealing initially with the history of publication of the letters and

how they gradually came to be seen as so significant. The publication in 1932 of the first collection of Lawrence's letters by Aldous Huxley was a landmark in this process.

In his letters 'Lawrence has written his life and painted his own portrait. Few men have given more of themselves in their letters. Lawrence is there almost in his entirety' (Aldous Huxley). This in itself is justification enough for the present edition. The letters are biographical documents of the highest importance in that they inform us about his discernible life; but, in addition, they contain unique evidence for the 'biography of an emotional and inner life' to which Lawrence referred in the Preface to his **Collected Poems**. Through them we come close to the creative mind and whole personality of the private individual, Lawrence. We also acquire an intimacy with the man and the spirit which played a public role and exerted a

formative influence on the modern consciousness. This influence, impossible briefly to formulate or precisely to estimate, is permanent. It has been variously welcomed and lamented; it is rarely denied.

Huxley focussed on producing a collection of letters alone, seeking letters from their recipients in *The Times* on 8th July 1930, the book published in September 1932 by Heinemann in London and Viking in New York. It reproduced approximately 800 letters, but not always in full. The title of the book, *The Letters of D.H. Lawrence*, suggested a comprehensiveness that it did not merit. There is no need here to dwell on the inadequacies of the book for example in terms of the omission of parts of the text of letters, or the omission of names.

Huxley describes Lawrence's "gift" and his "genius" passim in this first section of the introduction, seeing him as a "prophet." "Less than six pages from the end of his introduction Huxley abruptly brings this to an end and writes "Enough of explanation and interpretation," then provides four pages of reminiscence and ends with less than two pages on the letters themselves, which he describes as having the "highest importance as biographical documents [...] showing Lawrence as he was in his daily living [...] in all his moods." (*Lady Chatterley's Lover*)

The Cambridge University Press published Lawrence's surviving correspondence in full between 1979 and 2001. This has been supplemented by the publication in the *Journal of D.H. Lawrence Studies* of further letters, as they come to light. Such a commitment to publication reflects Lawrence's reputation as a highly skilled letter-writer. Such is the extent of the

correspondence, particularly full in his latter years, that it is an invaluable tool in understanding his life and works. Indeed no biography of substance can fail to refer to it regularly. Much has been written about Lawrence's skill as a correspondent.

Following the publication of the Harry T. Moore volumes, the momentum was kept up. The appetite for more letters, and therefore more information about Lawrence's relationships, was reflected in the publication of a series of complete collections of correspondence with individuals. Ignoring the not insignificant number of letters used in their own memoirs of Lawrence written in the 1930s by correspondents such as his sister Ada, Mabel Dodge Luhan, Catherine Carswell, John Middleton Murry, Earl and Achsah Brewster and so on, this had started in 1948 with the letters to Bertrand Russell being published, with those to Rachel Annand Taylor following in 1956. However, 1968 was a milestone year with James T. Boulton's edition of over 150 letters to Louie Burrows, none of which had been published before. Then in 1970 came the correspondence with Harold Mason, Edward D. McDonald and others at the Centaur Bookshop, the correspondence with Martin Secker and over 300 letters to Koteliansky. 1976 was another milestone year as the Black Sparrow Press published over 100 letters, comprising the then known correspondence between Lawrence and Frieda and Thomas and Adele Seltzer, nearly all of it previously unpublished, and in 1985 all Lawrence's correspondence with Amy Lowell.

We now have the Cambridge Edition of the letters. Including those published in the latest issue of the *Journal of D.H. Lawrence Studies*, there are 5721 letters. Lawrence

was the first modernist to have his correspondence published in full in an edition of this quality. As described in the Warren Roberts and Paul Poplawski 2001 bibliography, Lawrence was “one of the most voluminous English letter writers. The catholicity of his correspondence makes the letters an important source for study of the period, and the letters themselves are indispensable for an understanding of Lawrence”. Boulton himself was particularly complimentary. In the Preface to the first volume of the *Letters* he stated that:

The letters are biographical documents of the highest importance in that they inform us about his discernible life; but, in addition they contain unique evidence for the “biography of an emotional and inner life” to which Lawrence referred in the Preface to his *Collected Poems*. Through them we come close to the creative mind and whole personality of the private individual, Lawrence. We also acquire an intimacy with the man and the spirit which played a public role and exerted a formative influence on the modern consciousness. This influence, impossible briefly to formulate or precisely to estimate, is permanent. It has been variously welcomed and lamented; it is rarely denied.

Secondly, having established the accelerating impetus to have all Lawrence’s letters published, as they were perceived by editors to be of such significance, I am going to move onto their reception. When reviewing some volumes of Lawrence letters in the Spring 1971 *D.H. Lawrence Review*, Harry T. Moore noted that: “Everyone knows that Lawrence was a great letter writer, usually as “creative”

in his correspondence as he was in his poetry and fiction.”

Boulton in his Introduction to his *Selected Letters*, in part retracing the steps of his article “D.H. Lawrence: Letter-Writer” in *Renaissance and Modern Studies* in 1985, comments on the lack of any sustained evaluation of Lawrence’s letters and provides his own, by his own admission, too brief analysis. He identifies five attributes of the correspondence, which I will examine in the context of Lawrence’s correspondence with women. Boulton first identifies spontaneity, quoting Catherine Carswell’s remark that Lawrence “wrote letters as he spoke [...]. They fairly flash with quick life”. This can perhaps be done relatively straightforwardly with someone of similar background and views but he achieved it with those a of a wide variety of social and cultural backgrounds and education, from the Honourable Dorothy Brett, Lady Cynthia Asquith, Lady Ottoline Morrell and Baroness Anna von Richthofen to Giulia Pini, employed by Lawrence as a servant at Villa Mirenda, from Pulitzer prize-winning Amy Lowell and patron of the arts Caresse Crosby to post office clerk Blanche Jennings and tenant farmer’s daughter May Holbrook.

The third attribute that Boulton identified was sensitivity to landscape and natural beauty, also to be widely found of course in his other writings. There are many examples describing wildlife and plants. This one describes the surroundings of Lawrence’s cottage near Fiascherino, where Elide Fiori was their maid. He wrote to Cynthia Asquith in October 1913: But we’ve got an adorable place here: a little four - a beautiful palazzina in large grounds, that descend in terraces to the sea – that’s the Italian for it. I call it a little,

pink, four-roomed cottage in a big vine-garden, on the edge of a rocky bay [...]. It is a lovely position – among the vines, a little pink house, just above a rocky bay of the Mediterranean. One goes down in a towel to bathe. *And* the water is warm and buoyant – it is jolly. I wish you could try it too.

When so many critics struggle to find humour in Lawrence, it is a particular pleasure to provide examples of why they are wrong. Mark Kinkead-Weekes wrote at length on this in his essay “Humour in the Letters of D.H. Lawrence” in the 1996 essay collection *Lawrence and Comedy*. Boulton makes reference to this in the fourth attribute he describes, Lawrence’s witty presentation of human comedy. One of the best examples is Lawrence’s August 1917 letter to Esther Andrews, describing the awful concert put on by Meredith Starr in St Ives, which Lawrence had travelled from Zennor to see. Another is Lawrence’s partly mock rebuke for Cynthia Asquith’s folly in thinking that he and Frieda were blissfully happy, sent to her from Fiascherino in November 1913:

You say we’re happy – per Bacchino! If you but knew the thunderstorms of tragedy that have played over my wretched head, as if I was set up on God’s earth for a lightning conductor, you’d say, “thank God I am not as that poor man.” If you knew the slough of misery we’ve struggled and suffocated through, you’d stroke your counterpane with a purring motion, like an old maid having muffins for tea in the lamplight and reading Stanley in Africa. If

ever you hear of me in a mad-house, and Frieda buried under a nameless sod, you’ll say, “Poor things, no wonder, with all they’ve gone through.” You talk about tears drowning the wind – my God. – We are the most unfortunate, agonised, fate-harassed mortals since Orestes and that gang. Don’t you forget it. Put away all illusions concerning us, and see the truth.’

And the final attribute that Boulton identifies is the fact that several styles could be deployed in the same letter, or to different correspondents when describing the same event. As Lawrence wrote to Louie Burrows in December 1910:

“I wish you’d tell me which of my epistolary styles you prefer: the gay, the mocking, the ironic, the sad, the despairing, the elevated, the high romantic, the didactic, the emphatic, the bullying, the passionate, the disgraceful or the naïve, so that I can be consistent.”

In conclusion, we have seen the development of our understanding of the significance of Lawrence’s correspondence, and of publishing all that is available, both letters from him and to him. His letters have been analysed in general terms to show the wide variety of voices Lawrence used, and the high quality of his letters. However, to get further benefit from them and to understand better the relationships with individual correspondents, studies should focus on series of letters to them using the techniques now learned about how Lawrence mastered his epistolary skills.

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